

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF TYPES OF VOICE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The aim of the article is to set out the need for studying passive and active voices in English and Uzbek, as well as their translation from English into Uzbek. In English and Uzbek language, the aim of this Article is to present an overall classification of parts of speech, which are used as passive or active voices.

Key words: texts, teaching, passive voice, active voice, characteristics, reader, grammar, structure.

Abstrakt: Maqolaning dolzarbligi ingliz va o'zbek tillarida passiv va faol ovozni o'rganish va uni ingliz tilidan o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilish zarurligini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Maqolaning maqsadi - ingliz va o'zbek tillarida gap bo'laklarining umumiy tasnifini, passiv va faol ovozli tovushlarning qo'llanilishini ko'rsatish.

Kalit so'zlar: matnlar, o'qitish, passiv ovoz, faol ovoz, xarakteristikalar, o'quvchi, grammatika, tuzilish.

Most people, when studying their own language or a second language at school, are first introduced to grammar. That type of grammar is called normative or prescriptive because it defines the role of different parts of speech, and says what's a rule for "appropriate" use¹. When people are said to have good or bad grammar, the inference is that they obey or ignore the rules of accepted usage associated with the language they speak.

Language - prescriptive specific grammar is only one way to look at word and sentence formation in language. Other grammarians are interested primarily in the changes in word and sentence construction in a language over the years for example, how Old English, Middle English, and Modern English differ from one another; this approach is known as historical grammar. Some grammarians seek to establish the differences or similarities in words and word

¹ Galperin I.R. Text as an object of linguistic research. Moscow, 1981.

order in various languages². Thus, specialists in comparative grammar study sound and meaning correspondences among languages to determine their relationship to one another. By looking at similar forms in related languages, grammarians can discover how different languages may have influenced one another.

Still other grammarians investigate how words and word order are used in social contexts to get messages across; this is called functional grammar.

During this investigation while translating the Passive Voice from English into Uzbek we come across with the following grammatical difficulties:

1) Complete correspondence:

By complete syntactic correspondence is understood the conformity in structure and sequence of words in word combinations and sentences.

Example: New school was built in 1992 - Yangi maktab 1992- yilda qurilgan.

2) Partial correspondence:

By partial syntactic correspondence in sentences is understood the divergence in the order of words, omissions or partial substitution of parts of sentences.

Example: It's forbidden to smoke here - bu yerda chekish man qilingan.

In the absence of correspondence the constructions have no formal grammatical connection with the main parts of sentence, though these are always a conformity between them. The degree of attendance of action or conditions in predicative constructions determines the choice of complex compound or simple sentences in translation.

In the English sentences the predicative construction which function as an object is composed of a noun in the common case and an infinitive. In Uzbek this construction corresponds to the word combination " Eshik ochilganini va doktorni xonaga boshlab kirishganini" which carries out the same function though there is neither structural nor morphological conformity; it is a word combination expressed by a noun and participle. thus, an English predicative construction when translated into Uzbek gets nominalized.

The term voice in the collocation with the terms active and passive means something slightly different. The active voice is used in active sentence structures. The subject in such structures is typically the agent. The subject in passive sentence structures is typically the object of active sentence structures and has a passive role, which means that it does not cause the action, but is typically the "receiver" of it.

² Rogova G.V. Methods of teaching a foreign language in high school. Moscow, 1991

Example:

a) Mack attacked John. [active] - Mack Johnga hujum qildi.

b) John was attacked by Mack. [passive] - Johnga hujum (David tomonidan) qilindi

Example is in the “active” because the subject, Mack is in relation with an active role (the role of the agent). John is the one who performed the action.

Example is called “passive” because the subject, John, is associated with a passive role (the role of a “patient”), because John was the one on whom the action was performed.

The active and the passive voice and their occurrence. With respect to the English voice, there are two types, as was already mentioned. The passive voice consists of the auxiliary verb “be” and the past participle of a lexical verb³. The past participle can also be referred to as the “passive participle”. The occurrence of the passive will be considered in connection with tense and the type of sentence (question and negative statement).

E.g.- Butter is made from milk. -

When was the telephone invented?

Active voice and Passive voice.

They will fix the car tomorrow.

Ular mashinani ertaga tuzatishadi.

The car will be fixed (by them).

Mashina (ular tomonidan) tuzatiladi.

In conclusion, voice is the form of the verb which shows the relation between the subject, the object and the doer of the action. We have compared voices in three languages.

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³ Shakhova N.I. From the ability to read to the ability to speak. Moscow, 1972

